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Review Article

**ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE IN LUNG CANCER
SCREENING: THE FUTURE IS HERE****D. Hemalatha^{*}, K. Navyaja¹, M. Gurava Reddy², Dr. K. Venu Gopal³.***** B. Pharmacy, Krishna Teja Pharmacy College, Tirupati-517506.**¹Assistant Professor, Department of Pharmaceutical Analysis, Krishna Teja Pharmacy College,
Tirupati-517506.²Associate Professor, Department of Pharmaceutical Chemistry, Krishna Teja Pharmacy College,
Tirupati-517506.³Professor and Principal, Krishna Teja Pharmacy College, Tirupati-517506.**Abstract:**

Lung cancer remains one of the leading causes of cancer-related deaths worldwide, affecting the airways, bronchi, bronchioles, and alveoli. The rates of lung cancer are especially high among young smokers and people living in polluted areas, with an estimated 2.2 to 2.5 million new cases reported in 2023. Traditionally, lung cancer has been diagnosed using methods like biopsy, low-dose CT scans, PET-CT imaging, and X-rays. However, these methods can sometimes miss early-stage cancers due to various errors. Recently, the use of Artificial Intelligence (AI) has transformed lung cancer screening, diagnosis, and treatment. AI technologies, including machine learning, deep learning, radiomics, and natural language processing (NLP), have shown high accuracy in detecting suspicious nodules and analyzing clinical data, medical histories, genetic profiles, and demographics. AI can not only predict the type and stage of cancer but also assess the likelihood of future occurrences, reducing diagnostic errors and improving treatment options. Additionally, AI models have shown potential in using biomarkers and tumor markers to improve early detection accuracy. This review describes about the field continues to develop, overcoming current challenges will be key to fully realizing AI's potential in lung cancer diagnosis and treatment.

Key words: Lung cancer; Artificial Intelligence, Machine learning, natural language processing (NLP), multiple imaging modalities.

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INTRODUCTION:

Cancer is characterized by uncontrolled cell growth caused by a combination of genetic and environmental factors that damage DNA and disrupt normal cellular processes. Lung cancer, one of the most common types, is a leading cause of cancer-related deaths, primarily due to late-stage diagnoses. Lung cancer accounts for 1.8 to 2.0 million deaths annually, more than most other cancers, as shown in Figure 1. Even in early stages, lung cancer patients often have poorer outcomes compared to those with other cancers; for example, the survival rate for stage 1 lung cancer is below 70%. Approximately 90-95% of lung cancers originate from epithelial cells in the bronchi and bronchioles, with rare cases arising from the lung's blood vessels. Lung cancer is classified into two main types: small cell lung cancer (SCLC), an aggressive type accounting for about 20% of cases, and non-small cell lung cancer (NSCLC), the more common type, comprising approximately 85% of cases. NSCLC includes adenocarcinomas, squamous cell carcinomas, and large cell carcinomas [1]. The gold standard for diagnosing lung cancer is biopsy and pathological evaluation. However, pathologists and radiologists often face heavy workloads, which can compromise diagnostic accuracy. Recently, the integration of AI in cancer screening has shown promise in reducing errors and improving early-stage lung cancer detection. AI tools are increasingly being incorporated into clinical practice, marking a significant advancement in the digitization of medical imaging. With the rise of deep learning, AI has moved beyond initial hype characterized by inflated expectations and fears of replacing radiologists to broader use in clinical settings [2]. Thoracic imaging, in particular, has benefited from these advancements and has become a primary focus for AI software development. Various AI-based tools have been developed for tasks such as lung segmentation, nodule detection, characterization, and the monitoring of conditions like interstitial lung disease, bronchial disorders, and COVID-19. This article reviews the current applications and future perspectives of AI in lung cancer [3].

Figure1: Global Distribution of Cancer-Related Deaths in 2020

Progression of AI

AI, a term coined by John McCarthy in 1956, refers to the use of computers and technology to simulate

intelligent behaviour and critical thinking similar to that of humans. Research into computer-aided detection and diagnosis (CADe/Dx) gained momentum in the 1990s. At the core of AI is machine learning (ML), which uses algorithms and models to identify data patterns and make inferences without human intervention. There are two main types of algorithms used in this context, **Shallow Learning**: This approach requires large training datasets to function effectively. **DL**, this involves multi-level feature learning and utilizes convolutional neural networks (CNNs). In recent years, **imageomics** has emerged as a significant area of AI research. The process includes steps such as image acquisition, lesion outlining, texture extraction, feature selection, and machine modeling [3,4]. AI-assisted diagnosis has also led to the development of **pathomics**, which transforms pathology images into highly mineable datasets. AI facilitates complex data analysis, which is crucial for variant identification, classification, imaging, genetic diagnosis, and the prediction of genotypes [5].

Methods

Conventional Techniques for Lung Cancer Screening

Conventional techniques for lung cancer screening include various imaging methods such as computed tomography (CT) scans, X-rays, magnetic resonance imaging (MRI), and positron emission tomography (PET). Additional diagnostic tests include sputum cytology, biopsies, lung function tests, and endobronchial ultrasound (EBUS) [6].

Computed Tomography (CT): CT scan uses X-rays to create detailed cross-sectional images of the body. Unlike a standard X-ray, which captures only one or two images, a CT scanner produces multiple images and combines them for a more comprehensive view. This technique is more effective at detecting lung nodules than x-rays and provides valuable information about the size, shape, and location of any tumors in the lungs [6].

Magnetic Resonance Imaging (MRI): MRI operates similarly to a CT scan but focuses on producing detailed images of soft tissues in the body. Instead of using X-rays, MRI uses radio waves and a strong magnetic field to create images [7].

PET/CT scan: This method combines a PET scan with a CT scan using a specialized machine that performs both functions. The integration of these scans allows for easier comparison of the higher radioactivity detected in the PET scan with the detailed anatomical information provided by the CT scan [7,8].

The sample images generated by various conventional detection techniques are shown in Figure 2.

Figure2: Conventional methods in lung cancer screening.

AI Techniques in Lung Cancer Screening

ML: This foundational component of AI focuses on how computers learn from data. ML aims to uncover relationships within large datasets, leveraging techniques from statistics and computer science to develop effective computational algorithms. ML includes both supervised and unsupervised learning, which are essential for training models and defining learning objectives. In radiology, machine learning plays a crucial role in image classification and segmentation, using techniques like convolutional neural networks (CNNs) [9]. It also enhances quality control and image processing by reducing noise, improving image detail, and standardizing acquisition protocols. This ensures consistent interpretations and ultimately improves diagnostic outcomes.

DL: A subset of machine learning, deep learning involves multi-layered networks known as deep neural networks (DNNs). Inspired by the interconnected structure of the human brain, these networks consist of neurons that receive inputs, perform mathematical operations, and generate output signals. One significant advantage of deep learning is its ability to automatically learn features from raw data, eliminating the need for manual feature engineering. This approach has achieved notable success in image classification and segmentation tasks [9,10].

CADe/CADex: These systems are designed to assist radiologists in their evaluations, addressing challenges in the screening process. Using DL architectures, CADe systems enhance the accuracy of lung nodule diagnosis [11].

CNN: CNNs are used to extract informative features from images, employing global average pooling to summarize spatial information. Extensive experiments are conducted to evaluate the performance of these models, using benchmark datasets focused on lung nodules [12].

Vendor-agnostic deep learning algorithms have the potential to improve image quality and reduce radiation exposure. This is particularly important given the increased demand for chest CT scans during the COVID-19 pandemic [8]. One notable DL model is ClariCT AI (ClariPI), which operates in post-processing imaging and does not rely on projection data. Nam et al. indicated that for ultra-low-dose CT, vendor-agnostic deep learning models outperformed vendor-specific deep learning reconstruction (DLR) techniques. However, it is important to note that this study assessed image quality subjectively at a single radiation dose and did not consider diagnostic performance. Table 1 shows the results obtained in lung cancer diagnosis accuracy after combining AI algorithms with conventional techniques [13].

Table 1: Diagnosis of lung cancer using AI models.

Dataset	AI Algorithm	Outcomes
Low-dose CT scan	Deep learning algorithm	Diagnosis of lung cancer
CT scan of 200 lung nodules	Radiomics	Verify nodules as benign or malignant
FDG-PET imaging	Deep machine learning	Diagnosis of lung cancer using ultra-low-dose PET scans
Images and radiological features of 5251 patients from 14 studies	ANN SVM	Diagnosis of lung cancer
CT images of 9 NSCLC studies	Radiomics Deep learning	To diagnose whether patient had NSCLC
Pure ground glass nodules of 385 patients	Radiomics	Invasiveness prediction
Sub-solid nodules of 100 patients	Radiomics	Differentiate minimally invasive and invasive adenocarcinoma
Nodules of low-dose CT scan	SVM	Differentiate adenocarcinoma from focal pneumonia
301 lung cancer CT scans	CNN	Differentiate into squamous cell, adenocarcinoma, and small cell carcinoma
CT radiomics of 69 lung cancer patients	Radiomics	Differentiate NSCLC from SCLC
Pathological images of adenocarcinoma	Conventional deep neural networks	Predicted 10 most prevalent genes in adenocarcinoma
Serum biomarkers of 63 lung cancer patients	Artificial neural network modeling	Correctly classifying lung cancer patients based on biomarker panel

Application of AI in Lung Cancer Screening

The National Lung Screening Trial (NLST) has demonstrated that early diagnosis in high-risk populations can reduce lung cancer mortality by 20%. In this context, risk prediction is often more critical than clinical assessment. AI models have become essential in the lung cancer screening process, offering several benefits, including minimizing radiation exposure, accurately detecting and categorizing lung nodules, personalizing screening schedules, and facilitating low-dose CT (LDCT) interpretation in areas with a shortage of skilled radiologists [14,15].

Image Reconstruction Using Deep Learning (DL)

Low-dose CT scans are the only proven strategy to effectively reduce mortality in high-risk lung cancer patients. However, repeated scans can lead to cumulative radiation exposure. To mitigate this risk, techniques such as Model-Based Iterative

Reconstruction (MBIR) and Hybrid Iterative Reconstruction (HIR) have been introduced. These algorithms are widely used to reduce image noise and artifacts, although they have some limitations. DLR offers a promising alternative by reducing radiation exposure while maintaining accuracy, especially for patients requiring long-term follow-up. DLR not only reduces noise but also enhances image quality [16].

Radiomics in Lung Cancer Screening

Radiomics is emerging as a powerful tool in the qualitative interpretation of radiological images. Initially explored for conditions like rheumatic heart disease and pulmonary diseases in chest radiographs, its importance is now growing significantly in the oncological field. Radiomics allows for quantitative evaluations that complement traditional assessment methods, improving the accuracy of lung cancer diagnosis and prognosis [17].

Figure 3 illustrates how images are classified using AI-based models.

Nodule Detection Using CAde/CADex Systems

CADe/CADx systems rely heavily on DL. These systems first identify and classify suspected nodules as either nodules or non-nodules. The Lung Image Database Consortium (LIDC) is commonly used to analyze nodule characteristics such as morphology, density, and structure. As shown in **Figure 4**, in CT scans, a nodule is defined as a rounded or irregular opacity, which may be well or poorly defined, with a maximum diameter of up to 3 cm [18]. These nodules are crucial as early indicators of lung cancer and can be effectively detected and characterized using CT imaging, as shown in **Figure 5**.

Figure 4: Lung nodule detection on chest X-ray. A lung nodule seen on chest X-ray (A) is correctly detected by the deep learning-based computer-aided detection tool (box with orange borders in B).

Figure 5: Detection of a pulmonary ground-glass nodule. An axial chest CT image shows a 10×8 mm ground-glass nodule (arrow) in the right upper lobe. The ground-glass nodule is not detected by two different computer-aided detection tools based on classical ML methods (B and C) but is correctly detected by the tool based on DL (D).

Nodule Segmentation Using CNNs

Accurately segmenting lung nodules presents significant challenges due to their varying sizes and locations, especially when they are close to the edges of the lungs or adjacent to blood vessels. Segmentation systems differ in architecture, image preprocessing techniques, and training strategies. Various approaches are currently employed for nodule segmentation, including multiview strategies that analyze multiple perspectives of lung nodules to enhance neural network inputs. The type and shape of lung nodules influence the selection of segmentation methods, with several studies combining CNNs with advanced architectures to improve segmentation accuracy [18,19].

Nodule Characterization Using Radiomics

Radiomics offers a quantitative approach to the traditionally qualitative interpretation of radiological images. Initially applied in rheumatic heart disease and pulmonary conditions using chest radiographs, radiomics has increasingly gained importance in oncology. A key application of AI in characterizing pulmonary nodules is through accurate lung nodule segmentation, which is essential for automated volume estimation. This volume data is crucial for determining nodule management according to international guidelines and for calculating volume doubling time during follow-up CT scans [19]. Certain AI techniques for lung cancer screening not only detect and quantify lung nodules but also suggest Lung- RADS (lung-imaging reporting and data system) classifications.

Figure 6: Image generated by CT scan, which contains a lung nodule.

	Baseline CT
Location	LLL
Image number	#151
Type	Solid
Status	Baseline
Diameter	11.4mm
Eff. Diameter	783.7MM ³
Mass	N.A
4X Findings	
Lung-RADS	4A-Suspicious

Table 2: Automated Lung-RADS classification. Automated lung nodule detection, volumetry and Lung-RADS classification using DL based CADE tool in a patient who underwent an ultra-low-dose chest CT examination as part of a lung-cancer screening program.

AI Application in the Diagnosis of Lung Cancer Histopathological Diagnosis

Histopathological diagnosis, conducted through bronchoscopy or biopsy, remains the gold standard for lung cancer diagnosis. AI has demonstrated its ability to accurately classify lung cancer subtypes by analyzing digital pathological tissue sections. Additionally, AI models can predict survival prognosis

for patients with NSCLC. Numerous studies have shown that AI can assist pathologists in rapidly identifying lung cancer types, improving both the speed and accuracy of diagnosis [6 &20].

Cytopathological Diagnosis

AI-driven cytopathology diagnostic systems have been implemented for lung cancer classification and

diagnosis. Teramoto indicates a significant increase in accuracy when utilizing generative adversarial networks (GANs) [3,6]. The use of GAN-generated images for pre-training improved accuracy compared to previous studies that did not employ this approach. Their findings affirm the efficacy of this method for classifying cytological images, particularly when working with limited data. This approach involves the automatic generation of cytological images using GANs, which enhances deep convolutional neural networks (DCNNs) by incorporating both real and synthetic cytological images. As a result, this methodology improves the classification accuracy of DCNNs in lung cancer diagnosis [6&20].

AI and Genotype

AI can effectively manage the complex big data generated by genomics, helping geneticists and clinicians accurately interpret sequencing results. However, the applications of AI in this field are still limited, and further optimization is needed to enhance its effectiveness [6&20].

Biomarkers

Common biomarkers associated with lung cancer include Rb, K-RAS, EGFR, c-MET, TP53, ALK, and PDL1. Despite the identification of several potential biomarkers, their clinical utility is often limited by inconsistencies in diagnosis and prognosis prediction. AI-mediated proteomics is now exploring the use of multiple biomarker panels to improve the detection of various types of lung cancer [20].

Figure 7: flow chart representing the use of overall AI imaging techniques.

AI in Lung Cancer Treatment

Recently, AI has emerged as a powerful tool in the treatment of lung cancer. Models such as DL and radiomics have demonstrated significant potential in enhancing clinical decision-making. These AI tools provide quantitative insights into patient data, allowing for more effective navigation of the dynamic characteristics, individual variations, and inherent heterogeneity of lung cancer. AI can currently develop standardized treatment plans for tumor patients. One example is **Seq2Seq** (sequence-to-sequence), a DL algorithm that predicts weekly anatomical changes in lung tumors and the esophagus during radical radiotherapy. The performance of the Seq2Seq algorithm has proven to be more reliable in these scenarios. Biomarkers associated with susceptibility, such as oncogenes (LOH), DNA methylation, telomerase activity, and exhaled volatile organic

compounds (VOCs), are all elements used in early detection and diagnosis of lung cancer [21].

AI in Treatment Recommendations

Lung cancer lesions are treated using a combination of surgical and non-surgical modalities, including radiation, chemotherapy, and immunotherapy. Radiotherapy is particularly vital in lung cancer treatment, and AI has shown promise in optimizing this approach. ML systems can leverage high-quality data generated by radiotherapy, such as CT scans and treatment histories, to enhance radiation treatment planning. These algorithms can optimize radiation beam angles, predict dose-volume histograms, monitor radiation levels and toxicity, and develop clinical decision support tools. Such integrative predictive models hold the potential for personalized radiation treatments that improve both safety and efficiency [4&21].

Luo et al [3]. proposed an integrated learning collaborative filtering technique in ML to streamline the selection of therapeutic medications for personalized lung cancer treatment and identify potential drug candidates. Another initiative, **QUANIC**, utilizes large-scale multimodal and longitudinal data to create personalized models for predicting immunotherapy responses and resistance in lung cancer [8&21].

Immunotherapy poses challenges in patient selection and predicting treatment response. However, machine learning (ML) techniques, in combination with radiomics, have shown promise in improving patient selection and predicting treatment outcomes by providing non-invasive insights into the tumor and its microenvironment. ML algorithms have been utilized to identify factors influencing tumor immunogenicity and to create scoring systems for predicting responses to immune checkpoint inhibitors (CPIs) [13,15]. Additionally, predictive radiomic features extracted from CT images have been used to anticipate treatment responses. Kureshi et al. developed a data-driven model that achieved a predictive accuracy of 76% for tumor response to EGFR-TKI therapy in advanced non-small cell lung cancer (NSCLC) patients, considering clinical history, environmental risk factors, and EGFR mutation status. Liu et al. also developed a predictive model for overall treatment recommendations, achieving 65.8% consistency.

Radiomics, which involves the quantitative analysis of imaging features, has become a valuable tool for predicting individual responses to immunotherapy [16]. By capturing tumor heterogeneity and immune infiltration from CT images, radiomics allows for the creation of signatures linked to treatment response. ML markers derived from radiomics have successfully predicted immunotherapy responses in NSCLC patients, and integrating radiomics with DL further enhances its ability to identify responsive patients.

AI has also demonstrated potential in improving surgical risk prediction and assisting in treatment decisions. IBM Watson for Oncology (WFO) is an AI system that aids healthcare providers by extracting critical information from medical records, presenting relevant evidence, and exploring treatment options. WFO has shown a high level of consistency with recommendations from oncology committees, highlighting its value in supporting multidisciplinary teams [20&21].

DISCUSSION:

AI-based models for lung cancer diagnosis have made significant strides, offering objective, efficient, and

multi-angle approaches to assist clinicians. These models have the potential to reduce doctors' workloads, minimize misdiagnoses due to fatigue, and transform the current medical landscape by serving as decision-support tools. However, the application of AI in clinical pathology, particularly for lung cancer diagnosis, is still largely in the experimental phase and faces several limitations. Issues such as inadequate data quality resulting from non-standardized specimen processing and image annotation model reliability. Additionally, many AI models rely predominantly on pathological data without integrating other patient information, such as symptoms or test results, which weakens diagnostic accuracy. Furthermore, AI-assisted diagnosis systems for lung cancer still face challenges, such as missed or incorrect diagnoses of benign and malignant cases. The lack of data sharing between hospitals and inconsistencies in image annotation standards also complicate model training. Lastly, the legal framework surrounding AI's role in healthcare remains unclear, particularly regarding responsibility for mistakes made by AI systems. Clarifying these issues is crucial to improving AI performance and ensuring patient privacy protection in the future.

CONCLUSION:

Lung cancer is a serious disease that often requires early detection for effective treatment. This work highlights the transformative potential of DL, particularly through CNNs, in medical diagnostics. By automating the identification and classification of lung cancer, DL techniques can significantly reduce the workload for healthcare professionals and enhance diagnostic accuracy. This research provides a comprehensive overview of state-of-the-art DL methods for lung cancer classification, laying the groundwork for future advancements in the field. While the application of DL holds promise for revolutionizing lung cancer diagnosis, challenges remain. These include the vast scale of data sets and the lack of international standards. It is crucial to gather current data, apply DL and ML methods, and integrate both new and historical data. Despite these hurdles, researchers are actively working on tumor characterization, improving generalizability through transfer learning, and addressing biases in training data. Continuous learning is essential to keep pace with the evolving nature of cancer. AI-driven models for lung cancer detection have been developed, and while preliminary evidence supports the effectiveness of AI in diagnosis, many aspects still require improvement as the technology is in the clinical exploration phase. AI has the potential to enhance diagnostic accuracy, thereby addressing imbalances in medical supply and demand. As the field progresses,

overcoming existing challenges will be vital for fully realizing the benefits of AI in lung cancer diagnosis.

Future Perspectives

The development and validation of AI algorithms remain challenging due to the inconsistent curation of imaging and clinical data. However, advancing these capabilities is essential for the future integration of AI in clinical practice. Image generation in lung cancer stand to gain significantly from the evolution of AI, classical ML, and DL methods. Recent advancements in AI-based lung cancer detection, characterization, and risk stratification have shown remarkable effectiveness, comparable to histopathological evaluations. Automating time-consuming and repetitive tasks such as identifying image-based biomarkers and detecting lung nodules will become increasingly feasible with AI.

To fully realize these advancements, we need platforms that facilitate the selection of various AI applications and the integration of AI technologies into image archiving and communication systems for routine use. The future aims to create a cohesive pathway for AI applications in lung cancer screening, which will optimize the screening process. The first step involves pre-screening applications for personalized risk assessment, refining patient eligibility criteria. The second step focuses on image acquisition using low-dose protocols, enhanced by DL algorithms to ensure optimal image quality with minimal radiation exposure. The third step entails an AI-based system for automated nodule detection, alleviating the radiologist's workload. This process is followed by nodule characterization to distinguish between benign and malignant cases, optimizing resource use, reducing costs, and minimizing unnecessary biopsies or surgeries.

Limitations

One significant limitation of AI is the scarcity of large clinical datasets for training models, which can impede performance. While public datasets like LIDC-IDRI and LUNA 16 exist, they come with challenges such as data variability, as they contain images from a limited number of centres and may not represent the broader population. Additionally, these datasets may lack comprehensive clinical information and could include data annotation errors. The standardization of real-world data (RWD) is a promising step forward, particularly following the food and drug administration (FDA) passage of the 21st century cures Act, which provides a framework for using post-approval data in the development and training of AI models for newly approved drugs.

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Abbreviations

AI- Artificial Intelligence
 ML- Machine Learning
 DL- Deep Learning
 NLP- Natural Language Processing
 CT- Computer Tomography
 MRI- Magnetic Resonance Imaging
 PET-CT- Positron Emission Tomography
 SCLC- Small Cell Lung Cancer
 NSCLC- Non-Small Cell Lung Cancer
 CADe/CADex- Computer Aided Detection and Analysis
 CNN- Conventional Neuronal Networks
 EBUS- Endobronchial Ultrasound
 DNN-Deep Neuronal Networks
 DLR- Deep Learning Reconstruction
 NLST- National Lung Screening Trail
 LDCT- Low Dose computer Tomography
 HIR- Hybrid Iterative Deconstruction
 MBIR- Model Based Iterative Database Construction
 LIDC- Lung Image Database Consortium
 Lung RADS- Lung Imaging Reporting and Database System
 GANs- Generative Adversarial Networks
 DCNNs- Deep Conventional Neuronal Networks
 Seq2Seq- Sequence to Sequence
 VOCs- Volatile Organic Compounds
 CPIs- Check Point Influencing
 WFO- Watson For Oncology
 FDA- Food Drug Administration
 RWD- Real World Data